

Evaluation of In vitro Antioxidant and Antidiabetic Activities of Stem Bark Extracts of *Nothopegia racemosa* Dalz

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Received: Mar 27, 2026

Accepted: Apr 24, 2026

Published: Apr 27, 2026

ABSTRACT:

Background: The stem bark of *Nothopegia racemosa* (Dalz). was collected from Dandeli, Tinaighat, and Malsang forests in Karnataka, identified by a taxonomist. The stem bark is shade-dried, powdered, and successively extracted with solvents of increasing polarity. Extracts were screened for phytochemicals and evaluated for antioxidant activity (DPPH and hydroxyl radical scavenging) using ascorbic acid and gallic acid as standards, and for antidiabetic potential (α -amylase and α -glucosidase inhibition) using acarbose as the standard. All assays were performed in triplicate, and IC_{50} values were determined. **Results:** Phytochemical analysis confirmed the presence of tannins, flavonoids, glycosides, and polyphenols. Antioxidant evaluation showed that ethanolic and aqueous extracts exhibited better activity in both DPPH (IC_{50} = 172.36 and 71.18 μ g/ml) and hydroxyl radical scavenging assay (IC_{50} = 169.35 and 89.9 μ g/ml), though less potent than standards (IC_{50} = 20 μ g/ml). Ethyl acetate extract showed moderate activity in both DPPH and hydroxyl radical scavenging (IC_{50} = 366.52 and 330.8 μ g/ml). Antidiabetic assays revealed that ethanolic and aqueous extracts displayed marked inhibition of α -amylase (IC_{50} = 22.53 and 18.03 μ g/ml) and α -glucosidase (IC_{50} = 2.642 and 1.961 μ g/ml), compared to acarbose (IC_{50} = 3.039 and 0.316 μ g/ml). Among all, the aqueous extract showed the highest potency as antidiabetic and antioxidant property. **Conclusion:** The study highlights the significant antioxidant and antidiabetic potential of *N. racemosa*, attributed mainly to its phenolic and flavonoid constituents. The aqueous extract shows better activity, supporting its traditional use and a promise as a natural therapeutic source for managing oxidative stress and postprandial hyperglycemia.

Keywords: *Nothopegia racemosa*; Antioxidant activity; Antidiabetic activity; DPPH radical scavenging; α -amylase inhibition; α -glucosidase inhibition; Phytochemical screening

Introduction:

Medicinal plants have been an integral part of traditional healthcare systems and continue to serve as valuable sources of bioactive compounds for the development of novel therapeutic agents¹. The growing global prevalence of metabolic disorders, particularly diabetes mellitus, and the associated oxidative stress-mediated complications have intensified the search for safer and more effective plant-derived remedies². Oxidative stress plays a pivotal role in the pathogenesis of diabetes and its complications through the excessive generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which damage cellular lipids, proteins, and DNA³. Therefore, natural antioxidants capable of neutralizing free radicals and inhibiting carbohydrate-hydrolyzing enzymes are of considerable pharmacological interest⁴.

Nothopegia racemosa Dalz., belonging to the family Anacardiaceae, is a small tree indigenous to the Western Ghats of India⁵. It is traditionally used in folk medicine for various ailments, although its pharmacological properties remain inadequately explored. Plants belonging to the Anacardiaceae family are known to contain diverse phytoconstituents such as flavonoids, phenolic acids, tannins, triterpenoids, and other secondary metabolites⁶, many of which exhibit significant antioxidant and antidiabetic activities⁷. However, scientific validation of these properties in *N. racemosa*, particularly its stem bark, is limited.

The stem bark of medicinal plants is often a rich source of bioactive secondary metabolites due to its protective and structural role⁸. Preliminary phytochemical investigations of related species suggest the presence of phenolic compounds, tannins⁹ and flavonoids¹⁰, which are well-recognized for their ability to scavenge free radicals and modulate key enzymes involved in glucose metabolism, such as α -amylase and α -glucosidase. Inhibition of these enzymes delays carbohydrate digestion and glucose absorption, thereby contributing to glycemic control¹¹.

In vitro evaluation of antioxidant activity using established assays such as DPPH and hydroxyl radical scavenging assay provides insight into the free radical scavenging potential of plant extracts. Similarly, *in vitro* antidiabetic assays targeting carbohydrate-digesting enzymes offer a preliminary yet reliable approach for screening potential antihyperglycemic agents before *in vivo* investigations.

Despite the ethnomedicinal importance of *Nothopegia racemosa*, there is a paucity of systematic scientific studies focusing on its stem bark. Therefore, the present study aims to investigate the *in vitro* antioxidant and antidiabetic activities of the stem bark of *Nothopegia racemosa* Dalz., with the objective of providing scientific evidence to support its potential therapeutic applications and to explore its suitability as a natural source of bioactive compounds for managing oxidative stress and diabetes.

Material and methods

1. Plant Material Collection and Authentication

The stem bark of *Nothopegia racemosa* was collected from forest regions of Dandeli, Tinaighat, and Malsang in Karnataka, India. The plant material was authenticated by a qualified taxonomist, and a voucher specimen(KSCD/BOT/2023-24/20104) was deposited in the departmental herbarium for future reference. The collected stem bark was washed to remove debris, shade-dried at room temperature (25–30°C) for 10–14 days, and coarsely powdered using a mechanical grinder. The powdered material was stored in airtight containers until further use.

2. Preparation of Extracts: The collected stem bark of *Nothopegia racemosa* was washed thoroughly with distilled water to remove adhering debris and shade-dried at room temperature (25 ± 2°C) for 10–14 days. The dried material was coarsely powdered using a mechanical grinder, passed through a #40 mesh sieve to ensure uniform particle size, and stored in airtight containers until further use. The powdered drug material (500 g) was first subjected to defatting using petroleum ether (60–80°C) in a Soxhlet apparatus to remove waxes, fats, and other non-polar impurities. After completion, the marc was air-dried to remove residual solvent. The defatted marc was then successively extracted using solvents of increasing polarity: Ethyl acetate, Ethanol and followed by Distilled water (by maceration) each extraction was carried out for 6–8 hours until complete exhaustion of the material¹². The extracts were filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator. The aqueous extract was concentrated by evaporation on a water bath. The dried extracts were stored in desiccators and used for further studies¹³.

3. Preliminary Phytochemical Screening

All extracts were subjected to qualitative phytochemical screening to detect the presence of: Alkaloids (Mayer's and Dragendorff's tests), Flavonoids (Shinoda test), Tannins and phenolics (Ferric chloride test), Steroids (Liebermann–Burchard test), Glycosides (Keller–Killiani test)¹⁴. The tests were performed using standard phytochemical procedures¹⁵.

4. In Vitro Antioxidant Activity

4.1 DPPH Radical Scavenging Assay

The antioxidant activity was determined using the 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) free radical scavenging assay^{16,17}. Different concentrations of extracts (10–200 µg/ml) were prepared. 1 ml of extract solution was mixed with 1 ml of DPPH solution (0.1 mM in methanol). The mixture was incubated in the dark for 30 minutes at room temperature. Absorbance was measured at 517 nm using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Ascorbic acid were used as standard antioxidants. The optical density obtained with each concentration of selected test compounds and ascorbic acid was plotted on a graph. Concentration on X-axis and Percentage of inhibition on Y-axis. The graph was extrapolated to find the concentration needed for 50% inhibition and IC₅₀ was calculated.

Percentage inhibition was calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{ inhibitory activity} = (\text{Ac}-\text{As})/\text{Ac} \times 100$$

Where: Ac = Absorbance of control, As = Absorbance of sample.

4.2 Hydroxyl radical scavenging activity.

The hydroxyl radical scavenging activity of the extracts was determined by the deoxyribose degradation method^{18,19}. The reaction mixture (final volume 1.0 mL) contained 2-deoxy-D-ribose (2.8 mM) prepared in phosphate buffer (20 mM, pH 7.4), ferric chloride (FeCl₃, 100 μM), ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA, 100 μM), hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, 1.0 mM), and ascorbic acid (100 μM). Various concentrations of the test extracts (or standard) were added to the reaction mixture to evaluate their scavenging activity. The reaction was initiated by the addition of Gallic Acid and the mixture was incubated at 37°C for 60 minutes. Following incubation, 1.0 mL of 2.8% trichloroacetic acid (TCA) and 1.0 mL of 1.0% thiobarbituric acid (TBA) prepared in 50 mM sodium hydroxide were added to each tube. The mixture was then heated in a boiling water bath for 15 minutes to develop a pink chromogen. After cooling to room temperature, the absorbance was measured at 532 nm against a suitable blank using a UV–Visible spectrophotometer. The degree of hydroxyl radical scavenging was calculated based on the inhibition of deoxyribose degradation by the extracts. Gallic Acid was used as the reference standard. All experiments were carried out in triplicate, and results were expressed as percentage inhibition of hydroxyl radicals using the following formula:

$$\% \text{ inhibitory activity} = (Ac - As) / Ac \times 100$$

Where: Ac = Absorbance of control, As = Absorbance of sample.

5. *In Vitro* Antidiabetic Activity

5.1 α-Amylase Inhibition Assay

The α-amylase inhibitory activity of the selected plant extracts was evaluated using a modified dinitrosalicylic acid (DNS) method^{20,21}. The assay mixture consisted of 200 μL of 0.02 M sodium phosphate buffer (pH 6.9), 20 μL of α-amylase enzyme solution, and varying concentrations of the plant extracts (0–2500 μg/mL). The mixture was incubated at room temperature for 10 minutes. Following incubation, 200 μL of starch solution was added to initiate the reaction. The reaction was terminated by the addition of 400 μL of DNS reagent, and the tubes were placed in a boiling water bath for 5 minutes. After cooling to room temperature, the reaction mixture was diluted with 15 mL of distilled water. The absorbance was measured at 540 nm using a UV–Visible spectrophotometer. A control was prepared under identical conditions without the test extracts. Acarbose was used as the reference standard. The percentage inhibition of α-amylase activity was calculated using the following equation:

$$\% \text{ inhibitory activity} = (Ac - As) / Ac \times 100$$

Where: Ac = Absorbance of control, As = Absorbance of sample.

The IC₅₀ value, defined as the concentration of extract required to inhibit 50% of enzyme activity, was calculated.

5.2 α-Glucosidase Inhibition Assay

The α-glucosidase inhibitory activity of the selected plant extracts was evaluated using a p-nitrophenyl-α-D-glucopyranoside (pNPG) based spectrophotometric method with slight modifications. The reaction mixture consisted of 50 μL of plant extract at various concentrations (0–1000 μg/mL) and 100 μL of α-glucosidase enzyme solution (1 U/mL) prepared in 0.2 M Tris–HCl buffer (pH 8.0). The mixture was pre-incubated at 37°C for 10 minutes. The reaction was initiated by the addition of 50 μL of pNPG solution (5 mM). The reaction mixture was incubated at 37°C for 20 minutes. The reaction was terminated by adding 2 mL of 0.1 M sodium carbonate solution. The amount of p-nitrophenol released was measured at 405 nm using a UV–Visible spectrophotometer.

A control was prepared under identical conditions without the test extract. Acarbose was used as the reference standard. The percentage inhibition of α -glucosidase activity was calculated using the following equation:

$$\% \text{ inhibitory activity} = (A_c - A_s) / A_c \times 100$$

Where: A_c = Absorbance of control, A_s = Absorbance of sample.

The IC_{50} value, defined as the concentration of extract required to inhibit 50% of enzyme activity, was calculated.

6. Statistical Analysis

All experiments were performed in triplicate ($n = 3$), and the results are expressed as Mean \pm S.E.M. Percentage inhibition values at each concentration were calculated and used to determine IC_{50} values from dose–response curves using GraphPad Prism. Statistical analysis was carried out using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett’s multiple comparison test, and a value of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. The percentage inhibition data at different concentrations are presented to support the calculated IC_{50} values.

Results and Discussion

Preliminary phytochemical screening:

The preliminary phytochemical screening of the stem bark extracts of *Nothopegia racemosa* revealed the presence of several important secondary metabolites (Table 1). The results indicated that tannins, flavonoids, glycosides, carbohydrates, triterpenoids, and phenolic compounds were present in varying proportions among different extracts. Among these, the aqueous extract exhibited a higher amount of phenolic compounds, tannins, and flavonoids when compared with the ethyl acetate and ethanolic extracts. These phytoconstituents are well known for their antioxidant and antidiabetic properties and may significantly contribute to the observed biological activities of the plant extracts.

Table 1. Qualitative Phytochemical Analysis of Stem Bark Extracts of *Nothopegia racemosa* Dalz.

Phytoconstituents	Ethyl Acetate (EtOAc)	Ethanol (EtOH)	Aqueous (Aq)
Alkaloids	–	–	–
Steroids	–	–	–
Carbohydrates	–	+	++
Phenolic compounds	++	++	+++
Tannins	++	+++	+++
Glycosides	–	+	+
Flavonoids	++	++	+++
Triterpenoids	+	+	–

Note: (+): Present; (++): Moderately present; (+++): Highly present; (–): Absent

In Vitro Antioxidant Activity:

The antioxidant potential of the extracts was evaluated using DPPH radical scavenging and hydroxyl radical scavenging assays are presented in Table.2. Among the different extracts tested, the aqueous extract exhibited the strongest antioxidant activity, followed by the ethanolic extract. In the DPPH assay, the aqueous extract showed a lower IC₅₀ value (71.18 µg/ml) compared to the ethanolic extract (172.36 µg/ml), indicating better free radical scavenging ability. A similar pattern was observed in the hydroxyl radical scavenging assay, where the aqueous extract demonstrated stronger activity (IC₅₀ = 89.9 µg/ml) than the ethanolic extract (IC₅₀ = 169.35 µg/ml). However, the antioxidant activity of all extracts was lower than that of the standard antioxidants, ascorbic acid and gallic acid, which showed IC₅₀ values around 20 µg/ml. The comparatively higher activity of the aqueous and ethanolic extracts may be attributed to their higher content of polar phenolic compounds and flavonoids, which are known to act as effective free radical scavengers.

Table 2. DPPH and Hydroxyl Radical Scavenging Activities of Stem Bark**Extracts of *Nothopegia racemosa* Dalz.**

Extracts / Standards	DPPH Assay (IC ₅₀ µg/ml)	Hydroxyl Radical Scavenging Assay (IC ₅₀ µg/ml)
Ascorbic acid (Standard)	20.28***±0.0176	—
Gallic acid (Standard)	—	20.95***±0.03686
Ethyl acetate (EtOAc) extract	366.52*±0.0578	330.8*±0.3000
Ethanollic (EtOH) extract	172.36**±0.0801	169.35**±0.1528
Aqueous (Aq) extract	71.18***±0.0665	89.9***±0.2082

All values are expressed as mean ± SEM, n=3, **p*<0.05, ***p*<0.01, ****p*<0.001 as compared to standard group. One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison test.

Note: IC₅₀ = Concentration required to inhibit 50% of free radicals

Figure 01: DPPH and hydroxyl radical scavenging activities (IC₅₀ values) of various extracts of the stem bark of *Nothopegia racemosa* (Dalz.).

All values are expressed as mean ± SEM, n=3, **p*<0.05, ***p*<0.01, ****p*<0.001 as compared to standard group. One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison test.

Note: IC₅₀ = Concentration required to inhibit 50% of free radicals

In vitro antidiabetic activity:

The inhibitory effects of the stem bark extracts of *Nothopegia racemosa* on α -amylase and α -glucosidase enzymes are presented in Table 3. The antidiabetic potential of the extracts was evaluated using these enzyme inhibition assays, which are key targets for the management of postprandial hyperglycemia. The results demonstrated that both the aqueous and ethanolic extracts exhibited significant inhibitory activity against the carbohydrate-hydrolyzing enzymes. The aqueous extract showed stronger inhibition of α -amylase, with an IC_{50} value of 18.03 μ g/ml, compared to the ethanolic extract (IC_{50} = 22.53 μ g/ml). Similarly, in the α -glucosidase inhibition assay, the aqueous extract exhibited a lower IC_{50} value (1.961 μ g/ml) than the ethanolic extract (2.642 μ g/ml), indicating higher inhibitory potency. Although the extracts showed slightly lower activity compared to the standard drug acarbose (IC_{50} = 3.039 μ g/ml for α -amylase and 0.316 μ g/ml for α -glucosidase), the findings clearly demonstrate considerable enzyme inhibitory potential. Overall, the enhanced activity of the aqueous extract may be attributed to the presence of polar phytoconstituents, particularly phenolic compounds and flavonoids, which are known to inhibit carbohydrate-digesting enzymes and contribute to glycemic control.

Table 3. Inhibitory Effects (IC_{50} Values) of Stem Bark Extracts of *Nothopegia racemosa* Dalz. on α -Amylase and α -Glucosidase.

Extracts / Standard	α -Amylase Inhibition (IC_{50} μ g/ml)	α -Glucosidase Inhibition (IC_{50} μ g/ml)
Acarbose (Standard)	3.039*** \pm 0.0031	0.316*** \pm 0.002
Ethyl acetate (EtOAc) extract	34.85* \pm 0.3802	11.69* \pm 0.113
Ethanolic (EtOH) extract	22.53** \pm 0.0726	2.642** \pm 0.017
Aqueous (Aq) extract	18.03*** \pm 0.0218	1.961*** \pm 0.020

All values are expressed as mean \pm SEM, n=3, * p <0.05, ** p <0.01, *** p <0.001 as compared to standard group. One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison test.

Note: IC_{50} = Concentration required to inhibit 50% of free radicals

Figure 02: Inhibitory Effects (IC_{50} Values) of Stem Bark Extracts of *Nothopegia racemosa* Dalz. on α -Amylase and α -Glucosidase.

All values are expressed as mean \pm SEM, n=3, * p <0.05, ** p <0.01, *** p <0.001 as compared to standard group. One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison test.

Note: IC_{50} = Concentration required to inhibit 50% of free radicals

The enhanced activity observed in the aqueous extract suggests that water-soluble phytochemicals, particularly phenolic compounds and flavonoids, play a crucial role in the antioxidant and antidiabetic effects. These compounds may exert their action by scavenging reactive oxygen species and by inhibiting carbohydrate-digesting enzymes, thereby reducing oxidative stress and controlling blood glucose levels.

Overall, the results indicate that the stem bark extracts of *Nothopegia racemosa* (Dalz) especially the aqueous extract, possess promising antioxidant and antidiabetic activities, supporting its traditional medicinal use and highlighting its potential as a natural source for the development of therapeutic agents for the management of oxidative stress and diabetes.

Conclusion:

The present study demonstrates that the stem bark extracts of *Nothopegia racemosa* (Dalz) possess significant antioxidant and antidiabetic potential. Phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of important bioactive constituents such as flavonoids, tannins, glycosides, steroids, and polyphenols, which are known to contribute to these biological activities.

Among the different extracts, the aqueous extract exhibited the highest efficacy, showing strong free radical scavenging activity in both DPPH and hydroxyl radical assays, along with potent inhibition of carbohydrate-hydrolyzing enzymes (α -amylase and α -glucosidase). Although the activity was comparatively lower than standard drugs like Acarbose and standard antioxidants, the results indicate a promising natural therapeutic potential.

Overall, the findings suggest that *Nothopegia racemosa* (Dalz) stem bark could serve as a potential source of natural antioxidants and antidiabetic agents, supporting its traditional use. Further studies involving isolation of active compounds, in vivo evaluation, and clinical validation are recommended to establish its efficacy and safety for therapeutic applications.

Acknowledgement

We are grateful to BVVS Hanagal Shri Kumareshwar College of pharmacy, Bagalkot, and SETS College of Pharmacy Dharwad, Karnataka, India, for providing the necessary facilities for doing this work.

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